

GENDER STEREOTYPE AND WOMEN LEADERSHIP

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ABSTRACT

Gender equality has been a major issue among many scholars, scientists and conference theme across the world recently than in the past century. Despite the volume of academic papers and conference memorandum on the issue, women are still in the web of gender stereotype across the world with the worst experiences lingering in the third world countries or developing countries. This paper examines the factors responsible for gender stereotype against women leadership in organizations in Nigeria. Secondary data was examined and analysed by the researcher and the study found out that there is a lot of lack of fit expectations toward women which drives the gender stereotype against women leadership in organizations and the researcher concluded that gender stereotyping owes its origin to the gendered division of labour whereby the means of production and distribution is controlled by men within a patriarchal social, economic and cultural structure, and socialization of individuals, families and other institutions within such a structure is central to the creation and perpetuation of gender stereotypes.

KEYWORDS: Gender Stereotype, Women, Organization and Socialization

INTRODUCTION

Family life is characterized by roles which are gender based and this has exerted certain degree of influence on the workers' behaviour in an organization especially women in the third world country. Women are believed to have been given a natural place in the family with accorded roles which describe women as class of human who are to be led by men. The call of family duties is very visible that modernization and civilization are still struggling to push for needs for gender equality. The roles of women in the family have propelled gender stereotypes behaviour in leadership position in the work place. This is so because it is still within the sub-consciousness that no matter the level of educational attainment of a woman, the family roles influences the call for the place of service for a woman and not that of leadership. These domestic roles are influencing gender stereotype behaviour in work place toward women who aspire for leadership positions at their work place. The effect of this workers behaviour is gender stereotypes which are generalizations about the attributes of men and women as prescribed by family roles (Tabassum and Nayak, 2021).

Stereotypes are visible workers' behaviour in organizations which are found to be

generalizations about groups that are applied to individual group members simply because they belong to that group, and gender stereotypes are generalizations about the attributes of men and women. Gender stereotypes have both descriptive and prescriptive properties (Heilman, 2001). Descriptive gender stereotypes designate what women and men are like. Prescriptive gender stereotypes designate what women and men should be like. Both descriptive and prescriptive gender stereotypes, and the expectations they produce, can compromise a woman's career progress. Descriptive gender stereotypes promote negative expectations about a women's performance by creating a perceived "lack of fit" between the attributes women are thought to possess and the attributes thought necessary for success in traditionally male positions (Heilman, 2001). Prescriptive gender stereotypes establish normative expectations for men's and women's behaviour, resulting in the devaluation and derogation of women who directly or indirectly violate gender norms (Heilman, 2001; Heilman and Parks-Stamm, 2007). Whether functioning descriptively or prescriptively, gender stereotypes can impede the career progress of aspiring women especially in a patrilineal society.

Many gender-related barriers and biases have declined over the years but gender stereotypes continue to create problems in the progress of women's careers. The availability of opportunities for the career progressions of women continues to be negatively affected by gender stereotypes, which shape managerial behaviour and occupational outlooks in the workplace with patriarchal expectations. There are only 29 per cent women in senior management positions worldwide (IBR, 2020). The World Economic Forum (2017) suggested that an average gender gap of 32.0 per cent existed in four areas, namely, 'Economic Participation and Opportunity', 'Educational Attainment', 'Health and Survival' and 'Political Empowerment'. This shows an increase from an average gender gap of 31.7 per cent since previous years (Tabassum and Nayak, 2021). Despite many policies to increase gender equality in recent decades, gender discrimination based on gender stereotypes continues to exist. Gender stereotyping is considered to be a significant issue obstructing the career progressions of women in management.

GENDER STEREOTYPE AND WOMEN LEADERSHIP EFFECTIVENESS IN ORGANIZATION

- **Stereotype-based performance expectations toward women**

The negative performance expectations arising from "lack of fit" perceptions hold toward women can influence the way in which information about women in an organization is processed (Heilman, 2012). Expectations have a self-perpetuating quality; they tend to bias information in a manner that allows them to be maintained. Cognitive distortion enables them to withstand disconfirming evidence; cognitive distortion in what information is attended to, how it is interpreted and which of it is recalled (Heilman, 2007). Each of these has distinct consequences for employment evaluations and decisions which at the long run affects the effectiveness of the women workers within the organization.

Although the proportion of women in the workplace has increased remarkably within the past few decades, women remain vastly underrepresented at the highest organizational levels (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2011). Women occupy a mere 3.8% of Fortune 500 chief executive officer seats (Catalyst, 2012) and represent only 3.2% of the heads of boards in the largest companies of the European Union (European Commission, 2012). The numbers are

only slightly better in the political arena. In 2012 women held only 90 of the 535 seats (16.8%) in the U.S. Congress (Center for American Women and Politics, 2012b) and 19.1% of parliamentary seats globally (Inter-Parliamentary Union, 2012). Why are women so underrepresented in the most elite leadership positions? For decades researchers have proposed several explanations (Eagly and Karau, 2002; Heilman, 2001). One explanation for women's underrepresentation in elite leadership positions points to the undervaluation of women's effectiveness as leaders. This explanation is supported by several theoretical perspectives including “lack of fit theory” (Heilman, 2001), role congruity theory (Eagly and Karau, 2002), expectation states theory (Ridgeway 2011), and the think manager–think male paradigm (Schein, 2007).

Despite research showing that men may be perceived as better suited for and more effective as leaders than women (Carroll, 2006), some popular press publications have reported the opposite: that there may be a female gender advantage in modern organizations that require a “feminine” type of leadership (Conlin, 2003; Williams, 2012). The New York Times concluded that “no doubts: women are better managers” (Smith, 2009), and an article in the Daily Mail agreed (“Women in Top Jobs Are Viewed as 'Better Leaders' Than Men,” 2010). An article published in Psychology Today reported new data exploring “why women may be better leaders than men.

According to Williams (2012), the question if women's leadership style more suitable to modern organizations? The arguments for a “female advantage” in leadership generally stem from the belief that women are more likely than men to adopt collaborative and empowering leadership styles, while men are disadvantaged because their leadership styles include more command-and-control behaviours and the assertion of power. Yet, an academic discussion among leadership and gender researchers criticized the simplicity of these arguments, proposing that studies should not be asking whether there is a perceived gender difference in leadership but rather when and why there may be gender differences in perceived leadership effectiveness (Eagly and Carli, 2003; Vecchio, 2003). Vecchio (2002) discussed the importance of examining the leadership context, proposing that “advocates of a gender advantage perspective offer a simplistic, stereotypic view that largely ignores the importance of contextual contingencies”.

- **Stereotype-based expectations of information focused on women leadership**

Social psychology research has shown that expectations act as a perceptual filter, directing attention away from disconfirming information and toward confirming information (Heilman, 2012). Thus, information that is inconsistent with expectations often is not even noticed. But even when such information is noticed, it might not be integrated into the impression that is formed. It may be considered irrelevant or attributed to external factors or circumstances, rendering it not useful for forming impressions of an individual (Heilman, 2012). If expectation-inconsistent information is either ignored or attributed to something outside of the individual, the original expectation is not challenged and can be maintained. Research has provided support for these ideas, indicating that evaluators spend less time attending to work behaviours of individuals about whom there are stereotype-based expectations (such as women), than individuals for whom such expectations do not exist (Heilman, 2012).

Even if expectation-inconsistent information is attended to, its interpretation can

perpetuate initial expectations. Behaviours performed by individuals about whom there are different expectations have been shown to be interpreted very differently (Heilman, 2012). So changing a course of action may be seen as flexible when performed by a man, but as weak or indecisive when performed by a woman. Or delaying making a decision may be seen as prudent when the decision maker is a man, but as timid or passive when the decision maker is a woman. The meaning attached to a particular behaviour can vary greatly depending upon the expectations held. It has in fact been demonstrated that when targets are of different sexes, the implications drawn from their behaviour can be very different (Heilman, 2012). It also has been demonstrated that the kinds of words used in writing laudatory letters of recommendation for highly talented men and women are different, and in line with gender stereotypes (Madera, Hebl, and Martin, 2009).

- **Stereotype-based expectations by recall memory on women leadership**

People have been shown to recall more expectation-consistent than inconsistent information about another, even falsely "remembering" expectation-consistent behaviours that did not actually occur (Fiske and Neuberg, 1990). In fact, expectations have been shown to be more powerful than memories of actual behavioural events in making behavioural ratings (Baltes and Parker, 2000). These investigations suggest that a woman's behaviour that is consistent with expectations held about her is likely to be more readily recalled by evaluators, whereas her behaviour that is inconsistent with expectations is more likely to be forgotten. Biased expectations lead to biased evaluations, and these in turn become the basis of organizational decision making. The consequences can be damaging for upwardly mobile women.

- **Lack of fit, performance expectations and leadership career consequences on women**

The tenaciousness of performance expectations, and their powerful influence on the way in which information is processed, suggests that expectations produced by lack of fit perceptions can have important and broad-ranging consequences for how women are treated in the workplace. There are likely to be consequences for hiring, starting salary and job placement decisions as well as for opportunities for skill development, pay raises and promotions (Heilman, 2012). The expectation that women are ill-equipped to handle male gender-typed tasks and positions is likely to affect whether they are selected for such jobs and, if they are, the responsibilities they are given and the career track on which they are placed. Also, because of selective attention, interpretation, and recall, assessments of women's performance competence are likely to be negatively affected and, accordingly, their opportunities for advancement and attainment of organizational rewards thwarted. It follows that the more negative the performance expectations about a woman, the more gender bias should be evident. That means that the degree of the perceived lack of fit between the woman's attributes and the presumed nature of the job requirements, because of the expectations it produces, should also regulate the amount of bias exhibited. There is ample evidence that there are inequities in the recruitment (Gaucher et al., 2011), selection (Schmader, Whitehead, and Wysocki, 2007), evaluation (Eagly, Makhijani, and Klonsky, 1992), and promotion (Lyness and Heilman, 2006) of women. There also is strong evidence verifying the lack of fit formulation, demonstrating that the greater the perceived lack of fit between a woman and a

job, the more negative such evaluative outcomes they produce. In these investigations either the degree to which stereotypes about women are activated or the degree to which the position in question is seen as male gender-typed is varied.

- **Gender-type of leadership expectation toward women**

Lack of fit should only create negative performance expectations and subsequent negative evaluative outcomes for women when the job is deemed to be "male." This occurs when the work responsibilities are ones typically associated with men (Gaucher et al., 2011), and is highly likely when men constitute the overwhelming majority proportionally to women in the work place. The impact of gender stereotyping on women is evident irrespective of the level of position women belong to in an organization. However, it is more salient when managerial or leadership positions are concerned (Koenig et al., 2011; Kang, 2012). For example, studies (Tabassum and Nayak, 2021) found that both male and female respondents agreed that successful leaders possess characteristics commonly associated with men, such as leadership ability, competitiveness, self-confidence, objectivity, aggressiveness, forcefulness, ambition and desire for responsibility. By contrast, women are associated with qualities related to concern for the sympathetic treatment of others. These include being affectionate, helpful, friendly, kind and sympathetic, as well as interpersonally sensitive, gentle and soft-spoken (Eagly and Carli, 2007). Kanter (1977) cited in Tabassum and Nayak (2021) mentions that women in boardrooms may be regarded as 'token females' rather than as board members in their own right. Women, who are usually a minority in boardrooms, are often not listened to or valued on equal terms with male board members. Brescoll (2016) found that the participants in study considered the decisions of female leaders to be driven by emotions and therefore; they are less interested in hiring women in leadership positions. Similarly, Fischbach, Lichtenthaler and Hosrtmann (2015), investigating the Think Manager–Think Male paradigm, found that the emotions displayed by successful managers are the same as the emotions considered to be characteristic of men as opposed to women. The above discussion shows the stereotypical views on women as managers and leaders of organizations.

Over more than four decades, a number of researchers have explored gender stereotypes and requisite management characteristics (Heilman, Block, Martell, and Simon, 1989; Brenner, Schein and Muller, 1992; Orser, 1994; Schein, Mueller, Lituchy, and Liu, 1996; Elsaid and Elsaid, 2012; Berkery, Morley, and Tiernan, 2013; Tabassum and Nayak, 2021) following different paradigms of gender stereotyping to undertake research in different country contexts. The findings of these studies show that the stereotyping reported in the earlier studies continue to persist. Both men and women believe that men are more suitable than women in leadership positions, though this belief is endorsed more by men than by women. The findings also indicate that the Think Manager–Think Male mindset is a global phenomenon. A change in women's perception has been noticed in recent studies mainly in the USA where women have been less inclined to view management as the domain of men (Powell, 2011). Similarly, Stoker, Van der Velde and Lemmers (2012) found that although the general stereotype of a manager is masculine and although most prefer a man as a manager, female employees, employees with a female manager and employees working in an organization with a high percentage of female managers have a stronger preference for feminine managerial characteristics and female managers.

It is currently a fact that women are scarcely represented in senior management

positions in private companies and public institutions in the Western world, although it can also be stated that in the intermediate levels of the job ladder and in positions with a medium level of responsibility, there is a greater balance between men and women. In this work, following the approaches indicated by Hoyt (2012), we will attempt to identify the factors that can have an influence on the scarce presence of women in the upper levels of management. We will employ a thorough literature review to attempt to explain some of the reasons behind this situation. Over the course of history, an argument that has been presented to explain the scarce presence of women leaders is that the objectives or purposes of male and female lifestyles are different. According to this idea, men have generally channelled their leadership method to focus on the task, while women have done so to focus on people or the relationship. Male task-centred leadership has been more visible, more formal and official, and female people-centred leadership, on the other hand, has been considered a leadership of support. However, it is essential to analyze whether women universally tend to “focus on relationships” in their leadership style, and whether men tend to “focus on tasks” (Eagly and Johnson, 1990; Hoyt, 2010). In this sense, different studies have supported the hypothesis that there are gender differences in leadership styles and that leadership by women is more effective in contemporary society (Book, 2000; Vecchio, 2002). Some studies maintain that women lead and direct in a more democratic and participative manner than men (Eagly and Carli, 2007; Van Engen and Willemsen, 2004). Likewise, several authors have proposed the idea that women more often and more effectively use a transformational leadership style than men (Ayman, Korabik and Morris, 2009; Eagly, Johannesen-Schmidt and Van Engen, 2003). In the area of entrepreneurship, research has also been conducted that examines the influence of the gender variable on entrepreneurial activity (Brush, 1992; González Serrano, Valantine, Pérez Campos, Aguado Berenguer, Calabuig Moreno and Crespo Hervás, 2016; Minniti and Nardone, 2007; Ruizalba Robledo, Vallespín Arán, Martín-Sánchez and Rodríguez Molina, 2015; Ventura Fernández and Quero Gervilla, 2013). These works also reflect the existence of differences in the behavioural patterns in entrepreneurship according to gender.

FAMILY ROLES AND GENDER-STEREOTYPE ON WOMEN LEADERSHIP IN ORGANIZATION

Based on family roles performed by women, the society has described and prescribed women functions in organizations in respect to their care giving position. These roles have branded women as being emotional in some aspects of decision making.

Social role theory is considered to be significant in explaining the existence of gender stereotyping. According to this theory, managers have expectations about candidates relating to behavioural tendencies and activities which are concordant with their social roles and which can be based on gender, economic standing or other demographic subsets (Skelly and Johnson, 2011). Social role theory explains that men and women acting in accordance with their social roles are often segregated along gender lines and that this functions to confirm gender stereotypes (Koenig and Eagly, 2014). Because women are more involved in care-giving work, the characteristics ascribed to them are those of being nurturing, caring, and concerned with personal relationships. By contrast, men are typically seen by society as exhibiting masculine characteristics, such as leadership, strength and assertiveness (Vogel, Wester, Heesacker, and Madon, 2003; Skelly and Johnson, 2011). Candidates required for managerial positions are expected to have technical and rational expertise along with an acceptable level

of attributes which are perceived as masculine and those applicants who are more qualified and who are better able to fulfil the social expectations of a leader will be favoured more by the hiring manager.

Women may be perceived by some managers or executives as not possessing enough of the male-type or leadership qualities required for promotion to senior-level positions and this may hamper their progress (Skelly and Johnson, 2011). A study undertaken by Akanbi and Salami (2011) found that women's career advancement in management faces obstacles and limitations and gender-related preconceptions and biases, stereotypes and feelings about women's managerial and administrative abilities were believed to be the reason for these inhibitions. Surprisingly, it was found that the majority of the respondents prefer to work for men rather than women because women were considered as hard to work. The analysis also suggested that women managers were seen to lag behind their male counterparts in terms of possessing some significant attributes needed in managerial job performance and success. Therefore, the existence of stereotyping against females in leadership positions is proposed by the social role theory (Lyness and Heilman, 2006; Skelly and Johnson, 2011). Jain and Mukherji (2010) focus on the struggle of women to fulfil the roles of being a wife, a mother and a successful manager. They go on to highlight the impact of societal norms and traditions in creating gender roles for men and women in India where male characteristics are accepted as successful managerial characteristics and female characteristics are resisted. Bombuwela and Alwis (2013) have discussed how the career development of women is affected by the culture in Sri Lanka. Jamali, Sidani, and Safieddine (2005) mention cultural constraints in Lebanon and Pillai, Prasad and Thomas (2011) draw attention to the existence of social prejudice against women in Bahrain.

There has been a general attributed fact on the child bearing function on women which evident shows that women under this responsibility are or must be allowed to take this primary and socially compulsory responsibility which in-turn may or do affect the roles of women at the position of leadership. Despite equality and maternity legislation, maternity as a social role remains an area where women can face disadvantage, even if they don't have a family (Yaqoub, n d). Firstly, women of child bearing age may be discriminated against when it comes to recruitment decisions. Although not legal, it can be difficult to prove in cases where two candidates are equally or comparatively competent for a role but one is unlikely or unable to give birth. According to Yaqoub (n. d.), maternity rights give expectant mothers the entitlement of time off work for the birth of their child. In the UK, this is up to 52 weeks of paid leave. The Advisory, Conciliation and Arbitration (ACAS) service in the UK which seeks to support industrial relations, notes that maternity rights is an area over which they receive many enquiries and evidence suggest that it remains an area of concern (Yaqoub, n d). The Citizens Advice Bureau, who have similarly reported an increase in maternity-related enquiries, have listed the following common problems:

1. Singling out pregnant employees or new mothers for redundancy (particularly for sham redundancy situations).
2. Mishandling requests for flexible working upon returning from maternity leave (such as unjustified refusals).
3. Inappropriate comments about pregnancy that amount to harassment.
4. Health and safety breaches against pregnant employees or new mothers (such as a failure to carry out a risk assessment).

5. Penalising a woman who is sick during pregnancy (such as treating pregnancy-related sickness absence as standard sickness absence when evaluating their suitability for work).
6. Failure to communicate with an employee on maternity leave (such as not informing them of opportunities).
7. Failure to ensure the appropriate pay is awarded during maternity leave.
8. Failure to enable the employee to return to their old job after maternity leave, or another suitable and equivalent role if leave is more than 26 weeks.
9. Disadvantaging a mother in relation to training (such as that she might have missed while on leave).
10. Basing a recruitment decision on an employee's family situation (such as asking about their intentions regarding having a family, or childcare arrangements).

For the issue of the maternity among women, different organizations have different policies concerning the issue of maternity. Not all countries offer paid leave for women (Yaqoub, n d). For example, the US only guarantees 12 weeks unpaid leave for mothers in organizations of 50 or more employees, although some states and organizations offer more generous entitlements. Part-time workers can only secure these entitlements if they meet or exceed a threshold of 1250 hours worked per year in US (Yaqoub, n d). Furthermore, although employees usually have the right to return to their previously held position, if they are in the top 10 percentile of remuneration the employer can employ them at a lower level if they can demonstrate that it would be economically disadvantageous to have them return to their original position.

Extended periods of time away from the workplace to focus on the care of young children, which is typically experienced disproportionately by mothers rather than fathers, can exacerbate these problems, out-dating skills and affecting confidence. It also leads to assumptions about a mother's commitment to work, and her likelihood of taking time off to take on caring responsibilities (giving the impression of being less reliable), even if this is not actually happening. Care responsibilities can also extend to caring for elderly relatives and others in need of support and is therefore not restricted to mothers (Heilman, 2012).

Some organisations and professions can be particularly challenging in this regard, particularly where they require the 'ideal worker'; a worker who can prioritize their work, extend their working hours if required, even at short notice, because they are unencumbered by other responsibilities (Yaqoub, n d). This is seen to disproportionately affect women and mothers in particular, as they are more likely to be the primary caregiver or primary contact in an emergency. There is also variability worldwide in the levels of statutory childcare provision. Caring responsibilities often requires cares to take on flexible or part-time contracts, which can respectively be less secure and more poorly paid. They are also less likely to provide a foundation for career progression and promotion. The majority of flexible and part-time work is undertaken by women.

CONCLUSION

Gender stereotyping owes its origin to the gendered division of labour whereby the means of production and distribution is controlled by men within a patriarchal social, economic and cultural structure. Socialization of individuals, families and other institutions

within such a structure is central to the creation and perpetuation of gender stereotypes. There are theoretical attempts to break away from such a system by challenging existing patriarchal norms and values based on gender stereotypes. These structured and socialized stereotype formations have influenced the place and possibilities of women in the labour market with an extension to the space for women leadership position and organizational supports. Though there have been many attempts to theorize and scholarly analysed the situation toward gender equality among workers, the situation has been influenced socially prescribed roles attributed to women as a result of their functions in the family circle.

If women are to succeed in upper level work settings they have to violate gender stereotypic prescriptions. They have to be able to compete aggressively for positions, to act independently and decisively, and to take charge when the situation requires it. But such behaviours are counter to the directives inherent in gender stereotype prescriptions. When women exhibit these stereotypically male attributes and behaviours, they are seen as acting in ways that are reserved for men but prohibited for women, and disapproval and penalties result. Therefore, even when women seek to distinguish themselves from gender stereotypes and demonstrate that they have what it takes to fulfil traditionally male positions, they are likely to suffer negative consequences. But the women should and must stand up to leadership responsibility from family level through other social institution, to formal organizations like bureaucratic work place as a matter of complementing men efforts and contributing to success of the work force.

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